

Constructing Semantically Coherent and Interpretable Historical Vocabularies from
Domain-Specific Corpora: An Early Modern Dutch Case Study in Climate and Weather
using VOC archives

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Abstract

This article presents a semi-automated methodology to create historically interpretable vocabularies from large digitized historical corpora, using climate and weather terminology in the GLOBALISE corpus as a case study. Combining seed terms with word2vec expansion, followed by fastText enrichment, empirical thresholding, manual validation, and agglomerative hierarchical clustering, the workflow produces a versioned Early Modern Dutch Historical Climate vocabulary containing 256 canonical terms with 1,150 variants. In doing so, the article argues that static distributional embedding approaches remain valuable for historical vocabulary construction as they allow for transparent and reproducible category formation in linguistically complex historical corpora. Exploratory frequency and geographical analyses demonstrate how the resulting vocabulary can support large-scale study of climate and weather language in VOC archives while aiming to preserve interpretability and methodological traceability.

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1. Introduction

With recent and ongoing advancements in digitization and extraction of historical sources, large-scale historical textual databases have become available for analysis by historians and digital humanists. Optical Character Recognition (OCR) and Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) technologies use machine learning techniques to produce digital transcriptions of source material, which unlocks the potential to analyse historical texts at an unprecedented scale. Developments in Artificial Intelligence (AI) offer further opportunities in interdisciplinary collaboration of history and digital humanities. At the same time, these digitization efforts introduce new challenges for methodological approaches in areas such as Natural Language Processing (NLP) and computational historical analysis.

While these technological advancements enable the analysis of historical text-as-data, they also highlight fundamental challenges in understanding historical corpora. Sources often contain words and phrases whose meanings, usages and associations differ from present interpretations and research aims. Moreover, analysis of latent topics or themes not explicitly recorded in the historical sources requires a methodological approach to extract the relevant text. To explore these challenges, and to suggest a potential way forward, this article considers Early Modern (1610-1796) Dutch sources from the GLOBALISE project on Dutch East India Company Archives (*Vereenigde Oostindische Compagnie*, VOC) (GLOBALISE Project, no date a); (GLOBALISE Project, 2024), to build and present a vocabulary of climate- and weather-related terms. Constructing a vocabulary of climate- and weather-related terms is a first step toward reconstructing historical climate data. Such timeseries reconstructions can subsequently inform predictive models for present-day climate (change) research. The vocabulary also allows for geographic mapping (Section 5.2) and historical linguistic research such as semantic change analyses. The GLOBALISE corpus is a large and rich collection (transcriptions of over five million pages) that provides a varied linguistic database in which climate- and weather-related terms occur, for example as part of shipping logs. In constructing the Early Modern Dutch Historical Climate Vocabulary (v1.2), this article aims to contribute to the following research questions: How can analytically coherent thematic vocabularies be constructed from (domain-specific) historical corpora, whose structures, language and semantics do not necessarily align with present research questions? How can such vocabularies balance completeness and semantic precision, while also remaining interpretable and historically accurate? To this end, this article presents a semi-automated methodology: expert-selected seed terms are first expanded using Word2Vec (v1) and enriched with fastText (v1.1). These distributional embedding approaches are chosen deliberately for their transparency and suitability for historically noisy corpora, with fastText in particular providing robustness to orthographic variation. The resulting vocabulary is then post-processed using expert

validation, empirical thresholding, and embedding-based agglomerative hierarchical clustering to produce historically coherent categories, leading to v1.2.

The literature on historical climatology, also known as climate history, is as diverse as the various disciplines it encompasses. (Carey, 2012) summarizes the field of climate (change) history and historical climatology into four subfields: 1) scholarly contributions focusing on reconstruction of historical climates, 2) research on the social impacts of climate change and responses and adaptations to it, 3) literature on the uses (e.g. meteorological and climatological innovations) and abuses of knowledge on climate, and 4) perceptions and cultural constructions of climate. (White *et al.*, 2023) review recent advances in the field, highlighting continued research efforts toward climate reconstructions, with widening geographical scope including Southeastern Europe, Ireland, Latin America, Africa, Asia, and the Middle East.¹ They also point out the current scholarly interest within this subfield in studying extreme precipitation events, temperature, and short-term variabilities in global weather extremes following volcanic eruptions. Additionally, they identify recent research interest in interdisciplinary approaches, combining historical climatology and climate history with paleoclimatology and archaeology, economic and environmental history, to name a few. As part of the literature on climate history, it would be remiss not to mention the widespread use of Pfister indices: (Pfister, 1984) proposes a seven-point ordinal scale for monthly temperature and precipitation indices (from -3 coldest/lowest to 3 warmest/highest), which are widely applied in historical cases where quantitative climate data is unavailable but sufficient qualitative descriptions exists.² In a recent publication, (Camenisch *et al.*, 2022) demonstrate how historical sources can provide input for seasonal temperature and precipitation reconstructions in the Burgundian Low countries in the 15th century. To this end, they complement Pfister indices constructed through manually annotated information by an expert historian with Bayesian Statistics and existing climate models. The methodological approach proposed in this article can form a stepping stone in such approaches, as it proposes to replace the time-intensive manual annotation step with a semi-automated NLP approach, made possible by the availability of text-as-data, allowing researchers to extract relevant domain-specific information at scale. In this emerging intersection of climate history and NLP, approaches such as retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) leverage corpus retrieval with neural generation, but as found in (Yu *et al.*, 2025), these face limitations in interpreting historical terminology and socio-environmental dynamics. This article complements their findings by providing a systematic methodology to capture and interpret archaic, domain-specific terms. More broadly, NLP techniques such as named-entity-recognition and part-of-speech tagging have been applied to historical Dutch corpora (e.g. (Hupkes and Bod, 2016; Arnoult, Petram and Vossen, 2021)), and transformer models are starting to be developed (e.g. GysBERT for historical Dutch, (Manjavacas Arevalo and Fonteyn, 2022) and GloBERTise for the Globalise Corpus (Verkijk, Vossen and Sommerauer, 2025))³;

however, these approaches rarely focus on constructing historically interpretable, domain-specific vocabularies precisely due to the encoder nature of these models focusing on contextualized embeddings.⁴ By contributing to this gap, this article's approach enables historians and digital humanists to construct vocabularies based on large-scale textual sources for specific domains while aiming at preserving historical meaning.

Section 2 provides more detail on the GLOBALISE Corpus, its potential for studying early modern climate and weather, and the pretrained GLOBALISE Word2Vec model by (van Wissen and GLOBALISE Project, 2025). Section 3 describes the Word2Vec semantic expansion of selected seed terms, orthographic cleaning, variant clustering and semantic reallocation⁵ (v1), followed by the fastText model training and enrichment (v1.1), which together form Phase 1 of the proposed methodological approach. In Phase 2, as discussed in Section 4, the outcomes of Phase 1 are subsequently post-processed for HTR and other artefacts, and assigned an interpretive category for future research using agglomerative hierarchical clustering (v1.2). Section 5 presents the finalized Early Modern Dutch Historical Climate vocabulary (v1.2) and some exploratory analyses that apply the vocabulary. Section 6 concludes and reflects on future applications of the methodology proposed in this article.

2. GLOBALISE Corpus

The GLOBALISE Project uses automated HTR transcription software (Loghi) to provide digital transcriptions of the *Overgekomen Brieven en Papieren* (Letters and Papers, OBP; (GLOBALISE Project, no date b)). This archival series contains copies of VOC documents sent over from locations across the globe from the headquarters in Batavia (now Jakarta) to the Dutch Republic, from digitized scans available through (Nationaal Archief, no date), which is a subset of the overall VOC archives. The GLOBALISE corpus includes over five million pages of handwritten reports, letters, shipping logs, goods inventories and other documents during the seventeenth and eighteenth century that cover a wide geographic area roughly ranging from Yemen to Japan, including various locations in Africa and Asia (Petram and van Rossum, 2022; GLOBALISE Project, no date b). A pretrained Word2Vec model developed by the GLOBALISE Project team was developed for this corpus (CBOW, window = 5, min_count = 5, epochs = 5; (van Wissen and GLOBALISE Project, 2025)), which provides vector representations that are used in this article's methodological approach in deriving the first version of the Dutch Historical Climate Vocabulary. In v1.1, a complementary fastText model that was newly trained for this article on the same corpus is used to better capture rare words and spelling variants, leveraging subword information for Early Modern Dutch. The use of CBOW reflects the configuration of the pretrained GLOBALISE Word2Vec model; the fastText model uses skip-gram, which was selected

for its general better resilience in dealing with noisy texts as it uses only the token and not its surrounding tokens in the input layer (Mikolov *et al.*, 2013).

Apart from the rich and HTR-processed collection that GLOBALISE provides, the corpus was also selected for its inherent structural reason to contain historical climate and weather observations derived from the economic nature of the VOC. For example, shipping logs in the corpus were motivated to record wind and other weather conditions because they were necessary for navigation, monitoring the condition of transported goods, and the health of the naval staff. Additionally, due diligence for potential damages incurred to the ship or goods was partly the consequence of (extreme) weather events such as storms and heavy rainfall. For example, Figure 1 shows an excerpt of the shipping log for the ship *de Mars* in August 1667, that discusses near-daily weather conditions ranging from favourable on the 15th to tropical rainstorms and winds on the 22nd. Other documents, for example Figure 2 on Nassau Castle in Banda, record weather descriptions from land-based locations. As exemplified by these two cases, climate and weather terms appear repeatedly and abundantly in the GLOBALISE corpus, in part due to an institutional incentive to record weather conditions as they were operationally relevant to the economic aims of the VOC. Records from other sources in Early Modern Netherlands, such as municipal or church records, may also contain weather language, but do not necessarily capture the same geographic scale as the GLOBALISE corpus.⁶

Figure 1. Passage in log of the ship “*de Mars*”, excerpted from the *Overgekomen brieven en papieren uit Indië aan de Heren XVII en de kamer Amsterdam*, inv. nr. 1257 (scan 925), 1667 EEEE, *Tweede boek A: Batavia's ingekomen brievenboek, deel I 1667*.

Translated Loghi (HTR) transcription: 15 ditto Passed Poulo Canton with favorable weather. 19 ditto During the day we found ourselves N:W: to W: near the large island of Eijnam, and drifted quietly that day. 22 ditto with the day's heat lying Macoaousse Islands had storms and travat upon travat with rain and a heavy air became as if a large leak behind in the stern, around the rudder running water with noise inside, such that the pump ran continuously.

Figure 2. Passage recorded on the Nassau Castle, excerpted from *Overgekomen brieven en papieren uit Indië aan de Heren XVII en de kamer Amsterdam*, inv. nr. 1216 (scan 548), 1657 TTT, *Tweede boek 1657*. Translated Loghi (HTR) transcription: In the year 1655, December, in Nassau Castle, on Neira in Banda, on the 21st day of the month, with a light rain that was washed away by the rising sun, the daily work of the house and other tasks people, as well as that of the smith, continued as usual, and the Company's servants carried on transporting stone to continue the construction that had been started on the west wing of this castle.

In addition to the text on climate and weather available in the GLOBALISE corpus, this article's research questions are especially worthwhile to study in this domain. The domain of climate and weather cuts across physical phenomena, moral discourse, everyday descriptions and even metaphors and proverbs. Because of this ubiquity, the terms are rarely named consistently, resulting in historical fuzziness. Consequently, the domain exposes issues with polysemy, metaphorical drift, HTR transcription errors and artefacts, and the assignment of stable categories. The methodological approach proposed in this article therefore aims to balance the inherent fuzziness in both recall and precision.

3. Phase 1: Construction of Word2Vec semantically expanded and fastText enriched preliminary vocabulary

The initial phase of the vocabulary construction (v1 and v1.1) use static distributional embedding models to build and enrich first versions of the climate and weather-related vocabulary. These models are chosen over encoder transformers (e.g. BERT models) for three reasons. Firstly, the Word2Vec and fastText embeddings assign stable, type-level, representations that allow for the construction of a reproducible clustered vocabulary. Contextual embeddings shift depending on the surrounding text and therefore produce non-stable clusters, which is inherently at odds with the aim of this article to construct a fixed domain-specific vocabulary structured around different historically interpretable categories. This article specifically does not focus on research questions that contain a contextual element, for which encoder transformers would be preferable. Secondly, these distributional embeddings enable a transparent and reproducible methodological approach, that can be more easily applied and extended

by other researchers without requiring major computational infrastructure to use, compared to transformers which require more computing power and are more of a ‘black box’. Thirdly, the application of fastText as proposed in this article allows for a way to capture orthographic variation in Early Modern Dutch, through its use of subwords that can capture spelling variations, misspellings and HTR variations. Although encoder transformers can also consider subword tokenization, its contextual nature makes it less transparent to what extent it is successful in doing so for historical texts such as Early Modern Dutch, which often contain more substantial orthographic variation than modern languages (that are mostly used to train these types of models). Overall, the static and hierarchical approach outlined in the two phases were therefore preferred over transformers because they allow for category construction through clustering and provide more control over methodological decisions that can be inspected and reproduced in future research.

3.1. Seed terms, Word2Vec expansion and variant clustering (v1)

Prior to employing the GLOBALISE word2vec model (van Wissen and GLOBALISE Project, 2025), a seed term list was selected by the author to reflect potential terms in the domain of climate and weather in Early Modern Dutch, including possible historical spelling variants.⁷ Approximately 115 (positive) seed terms were compiled across eight categories: general weather (e.g. *weder, luchten, lughten*), storm (e.g. *stormwind, orcanen, tempeest*), rain (e.g. *regenachtig, reegenachtigh, regenbuij*), drought (e.g. *droogte, drogte, schraalte*), heat (e.g. *hitte, hette, sonneschijn*), cold (e.g. *sneeuw, coelte, vorst*), visibility (e.g. *mistig, nevelagtig, dijsig*) and a final category to capture the weather descriptions specific to shipping logs (navigation weather; e.g. *tegenwind, baren, windstil*). For each of these categories, several negative seed terms were also included as a conservative safeguard to potentially morphologically related but semantically irrelevant neighbours (e.g. *alweder, stormloop, bestorming*).

Using these seed terms and the pretrained GLOBALISE Word2Vec model, semantic expansion was performed. This involved retrieval of the top 75 nearest neighbours in the embedding space using the seed terms to form a raw first version of the v1 vocabulary. No problematic outliers were detected in this step, hence the next part of v1 construction involved cleaning and normalizing the raw output. This implied lowercasing terms, removing punctuation, the exclusion of a small set of manually identified noise terms, removal of duplicates within categories and the retainment of a short list of terms regardless of similarity scores. These similarity scores were calculated as part of a simultaneous orthographic clustering step that employed empirical F1 optimization of a curated set of positive and negative pairs to automatically select a clustering threshold. Next, a semantic reallocation step evaluated the alignment of each term’s embedding with the category centroid it had been assigned to and the alternatives, based on cosine similarity to category centroids computed from

the Word2Vec vectors. Reallocation occurred based on hardcoded thresholds, and an additional category for humidity was also introduced in this step. As an intermediary diagnostic, an overview of low confidence reallocations based on the gap in similarity scores (less than 0.10) was generated for manual inspection, which led to 1 manual override (moving *droogte* from its reallocated navigation weather category back to drought). The saved v1 version of the vocabulary consist of 270 canonical terms across nine categories, with 510 variants. Polysemy was explicitly allowed in this stage by assigning canonical terms both a primary and secondary categories to capture semantic diffuseness in the domain.

Several diagnostic evaluations based on the v1 vocabulary were performed on this frozen version, to assess how well it holds up both category-wise and more generally. Among other things, the results showed that many of the canonical terms were (highly) polysemous across categories, with only 27 terms mapping to a single category.⁸ Other checks that are not fully described here included a category coherence analysis (mean within-category similarity), a category separation analysis, a coverage analysis, and a spelling variant analysis. Taken together, these initial diagnostics suggest that, though constituting a workable first version, the v1 vocabulary is considerably polysemous and may also struggle to capture distinct categories neatly within the vocabulary (as shown in the category separation matrix in Figure 3). Based on the outcomes of a subsequent exploratory topic modelling exercise, which was not used downstream as it did not substantially improve recall, the performance of the Word2Vec model in relation to several elements relevant to the domain-specific vocabulary construction was examined, which motivated the exploration of using a fastText model for v1.1.⁹ This diagnostic check considered the semantic coherence across four general climate groups, and showed substantial variation among them. Keywords for hot temperatures showed a reasonable coherence (average cosine similarity: 0.554), whereas relatively weak coherence was found for the other three groups (temperature_cold, precipitation, wind).¹⁰ Additionally, four basic antonyms were examined to determine whether Word2Vec could distinguish contradictory statements such as ‘the weather is good’ vs ‘the weather is bad’. For all the semantic opposites checked (*warm* vs *koud*, *nat* vs *droog*, *helder* vs *donker*, *sterk* vs *zwak*), cosine similarity was relatively high, indicating potential issues in recognising antonyms in the embedding space.¹¹

Figure 3. Category separation matrix for categories in v1 vocabulary.

3.2. FastText training and enrichment (v1.1)

The diagnostic evaluations of the v1 vocabulary suggested that, while the Word2Vec-based expansion produced a workable initial lexicon, it showed limitations in capturing clear category boundaries and in distinguishing semantically opposing terms. In addition, the analysis highlighted substantial polysemy and variation in orthographic forms, suggesting that spelling variation remains a persistent source of recall loss in the embedding space. To understand if the use of subword embeddings could improve recall for historical spelling variations in Early Modern Dutch, a fastText model was trained that formed the basis for v1.1 of the vocabulary. This fastText model training performed for this article used the GLOBALISE corpus and skip-gram, with the following parameters: vector size of 200, window size equalling 7, minimum token count of 10, and 10 training epochs.¹² The larger window and lower minimum count were selected to yield more stable subword representations and to also include rarer terms in the embeddings, intended to capture spelling variations in Early Modern Dutch.¹³ The general diagnostics performed on the Word2Vec were repeated, and showed improvement in the semantic coherence, especially for the cold temperature and precipitation groups.¹⁴ Antonyms did not experience an improvement, a finding explored further as part of Section 4.2.¹⁵

Based on these outcomes, and the earlier Word2Vec outcomes, fastText was explored as a way to enrich the v1 vocabulary. For each of the existing terms, the top 10 nearest fastText neighbours were found, cleaned, and proposed as a candidate term if they were not already included in the existing terms from v1 in the first stage of the enrichment pipeline, and clustered based on orthographic similarity for manual inspection. Having passed this step by indicating sufficient potential for improved recall, the second stage performed the actual enrichment and integration into v1.1 of the vocabulary. Using a semi-automated process, fastText neighbours were again retrieved for the canonical terms from v1, but empirically derived thresholds for string similarity and embedding similarity were employed to find candidates for enrichment of the initial version of the vocabulary. The string similarity threshold of 0.73 was derived using a similar methodology as described in Section 3.1 based on F1-optimization using a small sample set of pairs. The fastText semantic similarity threshold of 0.771 was derived from the distribution of nearest-neighbour similarity scores across all v1 terms, calculated as the mean similarity minus one standard deviation (with a lower bound). It was also attempted to empirically derive the nearest neighbours as a function of observed variant counts in v1; however, this parameter was ultimately constrained by the predefined lower bound of 10.

The application of the fastText model to enrich the variants for the canonical terms identified in v1 resulted in enrichments for 241 out of 270 canonical terms, with a total increase of variants from 510 to 1853 in the v1.1 vocabulary. As an illustrative example for how this worked in practice, the word *travaat* is considered here. This Early Modern Dutch word meaning a short burst of wind paired with heavy rainfall (Instituut voor de Nederlandse Taal, 2026), was included across multiple canonical terms with variants in v1, as shown in Table 1. In v1.1, the recall has improved considerably from 9 terms to 32 terms (Table 1). The fastText enrichment implies that the vocabulary is now able capture more rare variants of *travaat* such as *travadigh*, *travaedt* and *travaetje*. However, this example also shows how the improved recall seems to have partially been gained at the expense of decreased precision, as potential HTR transcription artefacts and other noisy terms have also been included. The next section details the post-processing pipeline developed to attempt to counteract this loss in precision while maintaining the improved recall.

Table 1. Comparison of *travaat* terms in v1 (Word2Vec) and v1.1 (fastText-enriched).

Version	Canonical terms	Variants
V1	Travaad	“travaad”, “travaat”, “travade”, “travaden”
	Fravadig ¹⁶	“Fravadig”, “travadige”, “travatig”
	Travaet	“Travaet”, “travaten”
V1.1	Travaad	travaad", travaad,", "travaaden", "travaadig", "travaadt", "travaat", "travaat,", "travaaten", "travade", "travade,", "travaden"

	Fravadig	"entravadig", "fravadig", "kavadig", "kavadige", "tavadig", travadig", "travadig,", "travadig.", "travadige", "travadigh", "travatig", "vadig"
	Travaet	"travade,", "travaed", "travaed,", "travaedt", "travaet", "travaet,", "travaeten", "travaetje", "travaten"

4. Phase 2: Post-processing and historically interpretive categorisation

4.1. Post-processing and additional cleaning

As discussed in Section 3.2, there were clear improvements in recall for variants going from the v1 vocabulary to v1.1, especially in cases where Early Modern Dutch showed considerable orthographic variation. However, the improved recall was achieved partly at the expense of decreased precision; the fastText-enriched v1.1 also introduced HTR artifacts, truncations, and tokens with different types of punctuation attached.¹⁷ The first part of the v1.2 pipeline applies post-processing and additional cleaning as a methodological response to this trade-off (Vrooman, 2026c). This process aims to recover precision through a combination of rule-based filtering, empirically-optimised thresholding, and structured manual review, while preserving legitimate orthographic variation derived from v1.1.

The first stage of post-processing involved applying a set of strict linguistic filtering rules to the v1.1 vocabulary. These rules aimed to target the most unambiguous noise categories introduced while remaining deliberately conservative to avoid removing genuine variants discovered by the fastText enrichment process. These filtering rules excluded variant forms on the basis of containing trailing punctuation characters (.,:;!?(,,") characters, falling outside a character length range of 3-25 characters, containing non-alphabetic content beyond Dutch orthographic characters and hyphens, or starting or ending with hyphens or apostrophes or containing repeated instances of these characters.¹⁸ It should be noted that variants with trailing punctuation (e.g. *sonnescheijn,* and *teegenwin,,*) were not directly discarded immediately, but instead underwent a rescue step. If removing the trailing punctuation produced a form of at least three characters that passed the remaining validity checks, the cleaned form was retained. Moreover, rather than manually setting a string similarity threshold for variant inclusion, a validation set comprising 226 canonical-variant pairs (111 valid and 115 non-valid) was employed to derive an empirical threshold. This validation set was constructed by the author by combining reference tools, historical sources and HTR transcriptions. Terms were first checked against the *Woordenboek der Nederlandsche Taal* (Instituut voor de Nederlandse Taal, 2026), which is a historical dictionary covering Dutch words from 1500 to 1976. If this resource was inconclusive, terms were verified against the original digital copies of the historical

documents and their HTR transcriptions. The validation set was assembled across multiple passes to capture a broad range: combining a sample of notable example cases for the various issues, with core weather and climate terms stemming from the original seed terms across key domains, and a final inspection targeting cases not captured by the earlier passes. The empirical threshold optimised the F1 score, obtained at a string similarity of 0.79 (F1 = 0.679, precision = 0.575, recall = 0.829). At this stage, recall was prioritised over precision because a subsequent manual review step was designed to check ambiguous cases around the identified threshold. Variants that passed the strict filters but fell within an empirical review margin were flagged for this manual inspection based on the following criteria: initial mismatches between the canonical term and variant; a length difference of one character; and proximity to the threshold.

To handle variants close to the optimal threshold extra carefully, a review margin of 1.5 standard deviations of the similarity distribution in the validation set was calculated ($\sigma = 0.080$, margin = 0.121). All 65 variants falling within the resulting review zone (similarity range: 0.669–0.790) were flagged for source-based manual review, and subsequently assessed against the original digitized sources and HTR transcriptions. 24 (36.9%) of these cases were retained as genuine variants, 40 (61.5%) were removed as noise or semantically incorrect matches, and one case was left uncertain and conservatively excluded. Examples that were retained include *woei* as a variant of the canonical term *woey* (string similarity: 0.75), *dorre* for *dor* (0.75), and *wte* as an abbreviation variant of *weste* (0.75). Removed examples include *verdroagt* for *verdroogd* (0.778), and *frissec=te* for *frissee* (0.75), which were both HTR artefacts, but also semantic non-matches such as *gewreeven* for *gereegend* (0.778) and *regenagtig* for *bergagtig* (0.737). After applying the hard filtering, empirical thresholding, and manual review, the intermediary, post-processed form of v1.2 contained 270 canonical terms across nine categories with 1210 variants.

A final expert-guided cleaning sub-step was then applied to address any residual artefacts or issues that had not been resolved by the semi-automated variant filtering pipeline. Three types of conservative canonical-level interventions were introduced. Firstly, ten canonical terms were removed as they were HTR noise or had been confirmed as non-climate entries. These included certain temporal markers (e.g. *snamidd*, a truncated transcription of 's *namiddags*), place names (e.g. *Tamboa*), and other artefacts (e.g. *starm* for *storm*). Secondly, four canonical terms were renamed as they were confirmed to be HTR mistranscriptions (*slijve* to *stijve*, *fravadig* to *travadig*, *droag* to *droog*, *starke* to *sterke*). Thirdly, several multi-word seed terms, joined by an underscore, were removed from the canonicals as these cannot be represented as single-token embeddings. If necessary, single words from these seed terms were rescued and reassigned to a new canonical; this only applied to *brandende*, *brandenden*, and *brandender* from the original seed term *brandende_zon*. In addition to

cleaning up the canonical terms, one final check of the variants was performed: several forms with punctuation artefacts that were not caught in post-processing were dropped or cleaned (e.g. *vogtigh=t*), a few variants that were incorrect from a semantic point of view were removed (e.g. *landgrond* for *zandgrond*), and a final few HTR artefacts were removed (e.g. *boelte* for *koelte* with other HTR artefacts such as *eoelte* and *hoelte*). When rebuilding the lookup table, 27 cases in which the same variant form mapped to two different canonical terms were identified and documented as ambiguities, reflecting observed polysemy and orthographic overlap in Early Modern Dutch. After applying this cleaning sub-step, a vocabulary of 256 canonical terms with 1,177 variants was used as input for the agglomerative hierarchical clustering described in the next subsection.

4.2. Historically interpretative categorisation

As a final step, the last part of the second phase of constructing the Dutch Historical Climate Vocabulary re-focuses on the clustering of the canonical terms (Vrooman, 2026c). In v1, variant clustering was applied, resulting in distinct groups with names inherited from the original seed terms, which were again inherited in v1.1 and in the post-processed and cleaned intermediary versions in the second phase. While these semantic clusters were operationally useful during vocabulary construction, their labels do not necessarily describe the canonical terms mapped to them. In this part, these categories are therefore renamed to numbered semantic cluster codes (SC1-SC9) to acknowledge this mismatch while preserving traceability to the original seed term design. To support the use of v1.2 by (climate) historians and other researchers, an interpretable category schema attached to the post-processed and cleaned vocabulary is also needed, as this would for instance allow for temporal and geographical mapping of grouped terms within the vocabulary.

To obtain historically interpretable categories, agglomerative hierarchical clustering was applied to L2-normalised fastText embeddings (trained for v.1.1) for the canonical terms in the post-processed and cleaned intermediary vocabulary from the previous phase of this step. Several wind direction terms were separated prior to the clustering and assigned directly to a *wind_direction* interpretable category, as they carry no weather and climate-related information beyond their compass orientation. Three linkage criteria for agglomerative hierarchical clustering were evaluated: average, complete, and Ward linkage.¹⁹ Employing the average and Ward linkage produced similar partitions on the L2-normalised embedding space for the canonical terms; complete linkage resulted in a less balanced partition with a larger residual cluster for general weather terms and was therefore discarded. Ward linkage was ultimately selected for its use of minimization of within-cluster variance (Ward, 1963), which aligns with the aim of producing historically interpretable clusters. As shown in Figure 4, the optimal number of clusters (k) was determined based on a computed silhouette

score computed for k ranging from 4 to 12, which peaked at $k = 6$ (silhouette score = 0.0519). Overall, the silhouette scores were relatively modest across all tested values, which may reflect the continuous and semantically overlapping nature of weather and climate terminology in the embedding space, prohibiting sharp separation between clusters. The optimal level of six clusters yielded a sufficiently historically interpretable distinction among weather and climate phenomena represented in the vocabulary. The final clustering for v1.2 therefore used Ward linkage with Euclidean distance on the L2-normalised embeddings for the 243 non-wind-directional canonical terms at k equalling six. The inclusion of the new clustering approach also implied that the primary and secondary categories division assigned in v1 and v1.1 was no longer included in v1.2.

Figure 4. Cluster optimization plot based on silhouette scores for four to twelve clusters.

In addition to the interpretable cluster for wind direction terms, six interpretable clusters resulted from the agglomerative hierarchical clustering: *general_weather*, *heat_drought_desiccation*, *landscape_conditions*, *cold_wind_conditions*, *weather_temperature_conditions*, *wind_storm_sea_state*. These names were selected by the author, and are intended to reflect the dominant semantic content of each cluster rather than provide exhaustive coverage. The clusters *general_weather* and *weather_temperature_conditions* include terms that can be used in the context of various weather and climate phenomena, with the latter category including the term *weder* itself and a more prominent focus on temperature conditions. This motivates the choice to name the other category as the more general one. The remaining category names are more straightforward, reflecting different types of weather and climate phenomena. It is worth noting that in *heat_drought_desiccation*,

apart from words reflecting this category name, *nat* and some humidity-adjacent terms also cluster with this category.²⁰ Based on preliminary diagnostics of previous versions of the vocabulary, which showed that the model struggled to distinguish common antonyms such as wet versus dry, it is plausible that these terms co-occur in similar contexts in the VOC documents, and hence show distributional proximity to the heat and drought terms in the distributional (fastText) embedding space.

As Table 2 shows, the seed term categories do not map cleanly onto the interpretable clusters derived from the agglomerative hierarchical clustering. The original seed term categories were designed to be domain-coherent, but the fastText embedding space suggests that for some of the climate and weather terms, the corpus do not fall into the same strict boundaries. For example, *tempeest* was originally assigned to storm seed term category, then mapped to SC3 (humidity) in v1, before being returned to IC6 (wind, storm and sea state), while *schraalte* went from SC2 (drought) to IC3 (landscape conditions). Overall, Table 2 indicates that the clusters are relatively coherent for IC3 (96% from SC2) and IC4 (70% from SC1), while the others are more mixed, particularly IC1 that draws from a majority of the semantic clusters. This finding appears to indicate a certain degree of semantic diffuseness in the vocabulary, possibly resulting from the polysemous nature of Early Modern Dutch climate and weather language.

Table 2. Semantic drift: cross-tabulation of the numbers of semantic (rows; SC) versus historically interpretable clusters (columns; IC).²¹

	IC1	IC2	IC3	IC4	IC5	IC6
SC1	35	3	0	26	7	5
SC2	8	26	25	1	2	7
SC3	22	2	1	5	1	17
SC4	16	5	0	3	2	0
SC5	8	2	0	1	1	0
SC6	1	1	0	0	3	4
SC7	1	0	0	0	0	0
SC8	0	0	0	1	0	0
SC9	0	0	0	0	1	0

Figure 5. Dendrogram with highlighted IC clusters from agglomerative hierarchical clustering, showing canonical terms.

Figure 5 shows a dendrogram for the six IC clusters resulting from the agglomerative hierarchical clustering. At the top level, there are two major branches that broadly distinguish drought, landscape, heat and some cold terms from more general weather and rain, wind and storm conditions. The former is subdivided into heat and landscape versus cold, while the latter falls into the remaining three clusters. The relatively large linking distances could be explained by the diffuseness and polysemy of the climate and weather terms in the embedding space, potentially resulting in a not easily separable dendrogram due to an overlapping use of the terms across different contexts. In summary, these six interpretive clusters, together with the wind direction cluster, form the interpretive categorical layer in v1.2 of the vocabulary, that also retains the original SC names and codes for traceability. As will be demonstrated in the next section, the ICs can be used to analyse the geographic distributions of these categories within the GLOBALISE corpus.

5. Dutch Historical Climate Vocabulary (v1.2)

The Dutch Historical Climate Vocabulary (v1.2), as built through the successive phases discussed in Sections 3 and 4, is composed of 256 canonical terms that include 1150 unique variants of climate and weather-related terms (Vrooman, 2026c). The variants are distributed across seven interpretable categories derived from agglomerative hierarchical clustering: 401 variants for *general_weather* (IC1), 193 for *heat_drought_desiccation* (IC2), 171 for *cold_wind_conditions* (IC3), 140 for *landscape_conditions* (IC4), 38 for *weather_temperature_conditions* (IC5), 166 for *wind_storm_sea_state* (IC6) and 47 for *wind_direction*.²² To explore the operationalisation and the potential uses of the vocabulary for research on Early Modern history and Dutch language, two exploratory analyses are presented in this section: a term frequency analysis using the vocabulary of the GLOBALISE corpus, and a geographic analysis of the distribution of the vocabulary categories across proxied locations in the corpus. These analyses primarily serve as a proof of concept of the vocabulary, and to illustrate some preliminary distributional characteristics.

5.1. Term frequency analysis

To assess the distribution of the terms included in v1.2, a term frequency analysis was performed. This involved counting the occurrences of each canonical term across all inventories (nearly 7,000) in the GLOBALISE corpus, and ranking them across categories to identify the most frequent terms. The most frequently occurring canonical term across all inventory numbers is the term *weder* (1,249,194 occurrences), followed by *dewind* (161,768), and *vorst* (157,592; see Table 3 for the full top ten). *Weder* also shows the highest dispersion across inventory numbers, and the highest within-document frequency (columns 4 and 5, Table 3), indicative of both a broad distribution and repeated usage in the documents. This finding warrants care in reusing and reapplying the vocabulary, given that *weder* had multiple meanings in Early Modern

Dutch beyond weather (including again, against, and one of each; (Instituut voor de Nederlandse Taal, 2026)).²³ *Dewind* and *regens* complete the remainder of the top three for the number of inventories, with their dispersion suggesting widespread usage across the corpus. Apart from *weder*, within-document intensity is highest for *vorst* followed by *dewind*.

Table 3. Frequency distribution of v1.2 in GLOBALISE: top ten most frequently occurring terms.

Canonical term	IC	Total occurrences	Number of inventories	Within-document frequency ²⁴
<i>Weder</i>	IC5	1,249,194	6,843	182.55
<i>Dewind</i>	IC4	161,768	5,756	28.1
<i>Vorst</i>	IC5	157,592	5,065	31.11
<i>Regens</i>	IC1	121,130	5,549	21.83
<i>Wint</i>	IC4	79,755	3,711	21.49
<i>Winde</i>	IC6	55,532	5,346	10.39
<i>Moesson</i>	IC6	40,355	4,654	8.67
<i>Delugt</i>	IC1	39,419	3,977	9.91
<i>Nat</i>	IC2	29,347	4,948	5.93
<i>Gereegend</i>	IC1	28,066	3,829	7.33

As shown in Figure 6, the top ten canonical terms for each of the categories differ considerably in their comparative frequency. For example, the *weather_temperature_conditions* category is skewed by the dominance of the *weder* occurrences, followed by *vorst*, and with other terms making up a small portion. The *cold_wind_conditions* category is also skewed, towards *dewind* and *wint*, but less intensely compared to IC5. In addition, *General_weather* has *regens*, *delugt*, and *gereegend* as top three in terms of total occurrences; other top terms also seem related mostly to conditions observable in the sky or associated to wind conditions. The other four categories (IC2, IC4, IC6, and *wind_direction*) are comparatively more balanced in their frequency distributions of the top ten canonical terms. The *heat_drought_desiccation* category has *nat* and *droog* and *drogte* as their top terms, with *nat* likely surfacing here due to the difficulty of the two models in picking up antonyms in the embedding space, as discussed before. *Landscape_conditions*, composed of terms such as *schraalte* and *groeien*, is comparatively smallest in terms of total occurrences for top canonical terms. It is worth exploring in future research whether the prominence of both terms reflecting aridity and soil fertility can be related to agricultural motives in line with economic aims of the VOC. The category *wind_storm_sea_state* shows top three total occurrences for *winde*, *moesson*, and *stroom*. Taken together, the prominence of wind- and rain-related terms in IC1, IC3, and IC6 (and *wind_direction*) seems consistent with their importance for navigation in VOC shipping logs. Alternatively, it may reflect the observational priorities of record-keepers,

shaped either by navigational and economic concerns or by contrasts with weather conditions in their regions of origin (as posited in (Grab and Nash, 2010)).

Figure 6. Frequency distributions for top terms of v1.2 in GLOBALISE per IC.

5.2. Analysis of geographic distribution of the v1.2 vocabulary

The previous section considered overall top frequency distributions of the different categories in v1.2. In this section, the proof of concept for the vocabulary is extended by performing an explorative geographic analysis that considers spatial variation within the corpus. To gain explorative insights, locations were proxied based on the inventory descriptions.²⁵ For inventory descriptions with a single location (e.g. Batavia) mentioned (approx. 68.5% of the total), a geocoded proxy was plotted in GIS using the Places database by GLOBALISE (Pham *et al.*, 2025), supplemented with information from the GeoNames database ('Geonames', no date). Optimally, one would take locations identified through Named Entity Recognition, but at the time of this research, the GLOBALISE event and entity recognition was still being finalized, hence the decision to approximate the locations through metadata. These location proxies were then plotted on a historical map provided by the Rijksmuseum dated around 1700 (Janszoon van Santen, 1700).

Using the proxied locations, the v1.2 vocabulary was subsequently scanned across the same corpus and joined hits by locations, followed by aggregating the hits to obtain raw counts and relative frequencies per vocabulary category.²⁶ For scaling purposes, square roots were applied, which enable the geographical overview presented in Figure 7. As also shown in Figure 8, the 34 proxied locations ranged from the Middle East to Africa and Asia, with differing distributions of documents per proxied location.²⁷ Taken together, the pie and bar charts present several exploratory geographic patterns, that warrant future research with location-tagged text to provide conclusive findings. First and foremost, the information on Cape of Good Hope suggests a diverging pattern compared to most of the other locations: IC3 followed by IC1 show the highest comparative relative shares (32.6% and 27.2% respectively) in contrast to the general dominance of IC5 across the locations (Figures 7 and 8). This prominence may relate to a climatic difference between its location and the other locations across the proxies. For cold and wind-related terms (IC3), it could also reflect a particular interest in recording these types of weather conditions at a pivotal navigational point in travelling to Asian locations by VOC ships. For nearby Cape Town in the late eighteenth century, (Grab and Williams, 2022) provide evidence for, amongst other things, the occurrence of extreme wind force events and a high occurrence of days with mist and fog, which could also (partly) explain the observed difference.

Beyond Cape of Good Hope, the comparative relatively frequent use of terms relating to drought and heat (IC2) for Canton (19.3%, present-day Guangzhou; Figures 7 and 8) is also worth noting. Though explorative, this may relate to its difference in the updated Köppen-Geiger climate type; most of the locations in Indonesia fall under tropical rainforest or tropical monsoon climates (Af and Am), while Canton falls under the humid subtropical climate (Cfa) (Peel, Finlayson and McMahon, 2007). Out of the

locations in the Indonesian region, Banda stands out due to its comparative relatively substantial share for terms relating to cold and wind (IC3, at 24.5%) and wind and storms (IC6, at 12.1%; Figures 7 and 8). This could be related to its relatively more oceanic location, paired with monsoon presence, and the importance for the VOC to monitor wind conditions to arrive at the location that formed an important part of spice trade routes (Van Ittersum, 2016).

Figure 7. Georeferenced world map in 1700 with pie charts detailing the composition of IC categories per proxied location. Note: the size of the pie charts is proportional to the square root of the total number of hits for the v1.2 vocabulary per location, which are proxied from archival metadata.²⁸ Original map source: (Janszoon van Santen, 1700).

† Fewer than 10 documents: interpret with caution

Figure 8. Bar charts detailing the relative frequency of the IC categories per proxied location in GLOBALISE.²⁹

6. Conclusion

This article has presented a semi-automated and versioned methodological approach to constructing a domain-specific (weather and climate) historical vocabulary from a large HTR-transcribed corpus (GLOBALISE), and applied it to create the Early Modern Dutch Climate Vocabulary (v1.2). Starting with a set of expert-selected seed terms, the vocabulary was expanded using the pretrained GLOBALISE word2vec model (Section 3.1) and was subsequently enriched using a newly trained fastText model to improve recall for orthographic variants (Section 3.2) in Phase 1. Phase 2 involved applying a combination of rule-based filtering, empirically optimised thresholding based on a manually validated set of 226 pairs, manual review, and agglomerative hierarchical clustering to produce a historically interpretable vocabulary (Section 4). This version of the vocabulary consists of 256 canonical terms, with 1,150 unique variants, organised into seven interpretable categories. Two exploratory analyses (Section 5) demonstrated that the vocabulary can be operationalized to produce historically interpretable distributional patterns across the GLOBALISE corpus,

including (proxied) geographical variation in climate language on specific locations (Cape of Good Hope) that seem to be in line with secondary sources.

Several limitations of the v1.2 vocabulary and methodology should be noted here. Firstly, both word2vec and fastText struggle to distinguish between antonyms such as *nat* and *droog*, which show a high cosine similarity. This implies that the assigned vocabulary categories should be interpreted with this caveat in mind, especially for the IC *heat_drought_desiccation*, where humidity-adjacent terms cluster alongside drought- and heat-related terms (most likely due to their co-occurrence in the corpus). Secondly, as demonstrated in Section 5.1, the term *weder* appears frequently in the corpus, but due to its semantic ambiguity (referring to both weather but also again) this finding should be interpreted with care. Thirdly, the geographic exploratory analysis (Section 5.2) relies on proxied locations derived from inventory metadata. This implies that only single-location inventories could be included and that these form approximations of the locations mentioned throughout GLOBALISE. Once events and entities for GLOBALISE become available to identify locations across the corpus, a more precise and complete geographic analysis will be possible. Fourthly, the vocabulary was constructed and validated on the GLOBALISE corpus, which reflects specific institutional language of the VOC and the types of sources it contains (e.g. shipping logs). When applying the vocabulary to other Early Modern Dutch sources, such as personal diaries, municipal records, or ecclesiastical documents, it should be noted that the distributional properties of climate and weather terms may differ across such corpora.

In summary, this article makes two main contributions to the broader literature: 1) a methodological approach that can be applied more broadly³⁰; and 2) a vocabulary that opens new avenues for historical research within the GLOBALISE corpus. The versioned methodological pipelines require no specific infrastructure: the distributional embeddings used can be trained on any substantial HTR- or OCR-transcribed corpus. The combination of expert seed selection, iterative diagnostic evaluations, empirically grounded thresholding and agglomerative hierarchical clustering can be transferred to other domains, languages and time periods. This approach is particularly useful when the domain of interest is latent rather than explicitly labelled in historical source. In other words, it is useful when the relevant text is not consistently labelled or categorised in the records and appears in various document types. Potential research avenues to explore could be extracting historical disease vocabularies from administrative (medical) records, reviewing conflict terms in diplomatic correspondence, or economic language in trade documents. Depending on the period and language, challenges regarding orthographic variation, polysemy and cleaning may recur. By separating the main steps in different versions, the methodological approach proposed in this article allows for workshopping the parts of the pipelines relevant to other research aims and corpora. If applied to more modern Dutch and other cases with

more standardised orthography, the post-processing effort in Phase 2 is likely to be less extensive. In addition to this methodological contribution, the findings of the exploratory analyses raise new questions on whether the frequencies of certain climate terms and categories can be used to study climate variations and/or reflect VOC record keeping, which connect to broader debates in climate history. Other avenues for future research based on the vocabulary could include analysing of temporal changes in the use of climate and weather language, or, more ambitiously, conducting historical climate reconstructions.

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¹ A variety of scholars have also contributed climate reconstructions for the Dutch geographic area over time, see e.g. (Camenisch, 2015) on temperature and precipitation in the 15th century Burgundian Low Countries, (De Kraker, 2006; De Moel, Aerts and Koomen, 2011; Moerman, 2024) on flood and drought events in the past few centuries in the Netherlands. It is also worth noting here two other studies on the 19th and 20th century Netherlands by (Ekamper *et al.*, 2009, 2010) on the effect of weather events on mortality, and (Jennings and Gray, 2015) on migration and climate variability.

² (Nash *et al.*, 2021) provide an excellent and very detailed review of the literature on Pfister and other quantitative indices used in historical climate reconstructions.

³ Two recent papers consider the issue of changes in historical Dutch over time: (Wolters and van Cranenburgh, 2024) and (Debaene *et al.*, 2025).

⁴ Transformer models such as BERT produce contextual embeddings that shift with token's surrounding textual context, making them less suitable for constructing a fixed, categorized, vocabulary with stable assignments. They are better suited to downstream annotation tasks where contextual disambiguation is the goal. The beginning of Section 3 provides more motivation as to why transformers were not used in this article.

⁵ (Vrooman, 2026a) records the Jupyter notebook and resulting Word2vec-based first preliminary version of the vocabulary (v1) in JSON format. (Vrooman, 2026b) records the JSON of the fastText-enriched, but not yet post-processed or historically interpretatively categorized, v1.1 version of the vocabulary.

⁶ It is also possible that in these types of sources, weather and climate conditions are recorded more sparsely, and may be more often conflated with proverbs and sayings that contain weather and climate terms, compared to the GLOBALISE corpus.

⁷ The final list was compiled by the author, but preliminary analysis by Gerhard de Kok is credited here that was used to check and, where deemed necessary, supplement the author's initial seed term list. The full seed term list is available as part of the Jupyter notebook deposited in (Vrooman, 2026a).

⁸ The remaining distribution is as follows: 113 terms in 2 categories, 44 terms in 3 categories, 36 terms in 4 categories, 24 terms in 5 categories, 11 terms in 6 categories, 14 terms in 7 categories, and 1 term in 8 categories (*doorwajien*).

⁹ The v1 notebook (Vrooman, 2026a) provides a detailed overview of the explorative topic analysis approach, that builds on NMF and empirically optimized number of topics (*k*) selection to see if it could suggest additional candidate terms for a next iteration of the vocabulary. Given the relatively small number of candidates suggested through this method, in v1.1 the Word2Vec model was diagnostically evaluated and complemented with a fastText model.

¹⁰ Full results for semantic coherence based on cosine similarity for the Word2Vec model are: temperature_hot (avg = 0.554, min = 0.403, max = 0.702), temperature_cold (avg = 0.233, min = -0.074, max = 0.744), precipitation (avg = 0.190, min = 0.142, max = 0.236), and wind (avg = 0.319, min = 0.035, max = 0.713). The categories are as follows: *warm, heet, hitte, verhit* for temperature_hot; *koud, kou, vorst, koel* for temperature_cold; *regen, nat, vocht* for precipitation; and *wind, storm, bries, orkaan* for wind.

¹¹ The cosine similarity for the four checked semantic opposites for the Word2Vec model were: *warm* <-> *koud*: 0.7946, *nat* <-> *droog*: 0.5916, *helder* <-> *donker*: 0.5528, *sterk* <-> *zwak*: 0.6243.

¹² I thank Dr Gerhard de Kok for providing me with a SQLite of the GLOBALISE corpus for this article's fastText model training. The SQLite file contained parsed text and selected metadata for all inventory numbers with a year attached to it.

¹³ Given the motivation for selecting fastText in addition to Word2Vec because of its subword handling, v1.1 and downstream use the .bin file (not .vec) that saves the subword information.

¹⁴ For fastText, the semantic coherence check showed the following cosine similarity scores for the same categories evaluated for the Word2Vec model: temperature_hot (avg = 0.615, min = 0.550, max = 0.693), temperature_cold (avg = 0.364, min = 0.183, max = 0.564), precipitation (avg = 0.422, min = 0.340, max = 0.503), and wind (avg = 0.363, min = 0.077, max = 0.682)

¹⁵ Cosine similarity for the fastText concerning the same antonyms checked before were found to be: *warm* <-> *koud*: 0.7465, *nat* <-> *droog*: 0.6776, *helder* <-> *donker*: 0.5734, *sterk* <-> *zwak*: 0.6236.

¹⁶ HTR transcriptions that have been manually checked seem to confuse the t and f in Early Modern Dutch handwriting.

¹⁷ With the knowledge of hindsight, in replicating this approach to similar corpora one could also consider (conservatively) applying part of the post-processing steps, e.g. the cleaning (and if necessary rescuing) of tokens with punctuation attached, in the training of the fastText embeddings for v1.1.

¹⁸ Punctuation-attached tokens were not removed prior to model training, as a precaution to avoid inadvertently discarding legitimate orthographic variants in a corpus that is inevitably noisy due to HTR. The post-processing pipeline therefore handles this conservatively through the cleaning and filtering part of v1.2. It should be noted that the „ character functions as a line-continuation marker in the GLOBALISE HTR output; the rescue step recovers these if the cleaned version that strips the trailing marker meets the thresholds. However, fragments opening with this character are lost to a line break and therefore are not reconstructed but dropped in this step.

¹⁹ For more details on these types of linkages for hierarchical clustering, consider (Nielsen, 2016).

²⁰ In reviewing the Word2Vec and fastText models for v1.1, the cosine similarity of several general semantic opposites were checked. For *nat* versus *droog*, the W2V and FT similarity equalled 0.5916 and 0.6776 respectively, while *warm* versus *koud* showed comparably high levels of cosine similarity at 0.7946 (W2V) and 0.7465 (FT). Antonyms for bright versus dark and strong versus weak were also checked to assess whether this issue related to antonyms beyond weather, and similarly highly cosine similarity levels were found. This suggests that the issue is not domain-specific, but rather reflects a broader issue in detecting antonyms.

²¹ In numerical order, the different clusters from this part of the v1.2 pipeline are: cold, drought, humidity, heat, rain, navigation_weather, storm, visibility and weather_general for the SC clusters, and general_weather, heat_drought_desiccation, landscape_conditions, cold_wind_conditions, weather_temperature_conditions, wind_storm_sea_state for the IC clusters.

²² Summing up the variants for individual categories gives a total of 1156 variants, with 6 variants being polysemous in cross-category terms.

²³ The semantic ambiguousness of *weder* in future uses could for instance be disentangled by considering contextual embeddings.

²⁴ This measure is intended to reflect the intensity with which the canonical term is used in the corpus, and is calculated as follows: $occurrence_d = round(\frac{c}{\max(d,1)}, 2)$, where *d* stands for the number of documents that include the term, and *c* for the total occurrence of the term.

²⁵ The metadata evaluation and georeferencing of the proxied locations was performed by Meke R. Goedhart, the data curator of the Huygens HEAT project.

²⁶ Relative frequencies were calculated as follows: $rf_{i,c} = (\frac{n_{i,c}}{n_{i}^{total}} \cdot 100)$, where *n* equals the raw count and n^{total} the total number of hits across all categories, both for location *i* and category *c*. To avoid division by zero, the denominator is defined to be replaced by NaN if equal to zero.

²⁷ Proxied locations with a number of documents lower than 10 are marked in Figure 8, and include for example Japan, China, and Arabia and the Moluccas.

²⁸ I thank Meke R. Goedhart for procuring the metadata of the GLOBALISE dataset used to proxy the locations, and for georeferencing and plotting the locations in the base map used for the figure. The database of inventory numbers with a single location, based on an overall database that filtered whether one or more locations were present in the description of an inventory, consist of approximately 68.5% of the inventory numbers, and include both locations (e.g. Cape of Good Hope) and areas (e.g. Coromandel, Persia). For the geolocating, the Places dataset of GLOBALISE was used as a base (Pham *et al.*, 2025), supplemented with data curation for missing locations using Geonames. The high-resolution image of the historical map was provided by the Rijksmuseum (Janszoon van Santen, 1700).

²⁹ Names correspond to the spelling in the original documents and/or the Places and GeoNames databases consulted. For ease, the locations mentioned in-text are translated to English.

³⁰ The Jupyter Notebooks in (Vrooman, 2026a, 2026b, 2026c) provide step-by-step overviews with explanations to apply the proposed methodology.